

Attitude of Youth to Sales of Arms ... (Iniobong, 2023) DOI:

Attitude of Youth to Sales of Arms and Ammunition in Riverine Areas of Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

This study examines attitude of youth to sales of arms and ammunition in riverine areas of Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State. This study adopted the survey research design. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 150 youths in Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State. One instrument was used for data collection: Questionnaire on Sale of Arms and Ammunition Questionnaire ($r=0.78$). Data collected were analysed using percentage scores, mean and standard deviation. Findings of the study revealed a weighted mean of 2.56 which is greater than the threshold set at 2.50; this signifies a positive attitude to sales of arms and ammunition among youth in Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that government should provide job opportunities for the unemployed youths in the country. Security personnel should be more proactive in maintaining peace in the country. Youths should not be allowed to legalize the selling of arms and ammunition in the country. Anyone caught with unlawful possession of arms and ammunition should be arrested and charged to court. Community leaders should work with government in maintaining peace and they should not condone criminals or criminal acts in their domain.

Keywords: Arms, Ammunition, Nigerian Youths, Riverine Areas

Introduction

Youth varies from culture to culture and from society to society. In most societies in Nigeria, the progression from childhood to youth involves some systematic rites of passage. These rites have symbolic importance in that, simply by participating in them, an individual achieves a new status and position. Such new status gains validity through genuine community action and recognition. Globally, youth is described as the time in individual's life and this runs between and the end of childhood and the entry into the world of work (Onyekwusi & Effiong, 2002). However, youth all over the world are important part of the society in which they live. A disciplined, focus and law-abiding youth can create a bright future for any nation. Conversely, a lawless indulgent and violent youth is a greater threat to a nation's peace and security. According to the report of the Political Bureau (1997) in Abdullahi (2003), classified youths as those between six years to 30 years. This refers to the classification conforms to the formal education years, tampering with which may endanger the youth's life and subsequently the larger society. Therefore, youths are termed as the active category from which so much is expected to achieve the societal goals like economic prosperity, political stability, and social justice. The National Youth Development Policy (2001) defines youth as people aged 18-35 years. Youth occupy a prominent place in any society. Apart from being the owners and leaders of tomorrow, they outnumber the middle-aged and aged (Onyekpe, 2007). Onyekpe added that, besides numerical superiority, youth have energy and ideas that are society's great potentials.

Moreover, The National Youth Development Policy (2001) asserts that youths are the foundation of a society. Their energies, inventiveness, character and orientation define the pace of development and security of a nation. Through their creative talents and labour power a nation can make giant stride in economic development and socio-political attainments. In their dreams and hopes, a nation finds her motivation; on their energies, she builds her vitality and purpose, and because of their dreams and aspirations, the future of a nation is assured. World Health Organization (2007) define "young people" as people between the ages of 10 and 24. Youth participation in development projects helps build their confidence and their ability to express themselves, it helps them make their own decisions, it helps them grow up to be active citizens, it enhances their understanding of issues which affect their society. At a personal level participation can increase the youth knowledge and practical skills that come from real life problem solving. It can also strengthen their social interest and nurture long term commitment to self fulfilment. It enables the youth to think critically and actively challenge situations.

The statement above acknowledges the role of the youth in the peace, development and security of the nation. As the most active segment of any society; youth are the major determinants of peace and stability of a nation (Ozohu-Sulaiman,

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2006). Peace is a state of tranquility which all human beings seek. No nation can record any meaningful feat of development without relative peace. Adedjoja and Fakokunde (2010) revealed that for any reasonable progress to be made in human life, peace must prevail. The level of restiveness and violence prevailing at individual, family, communal, national and international levels made it a necessity to build a culture of peace. If culture is a total way of life of a people, it means a culture of peace must be cultivated. Youths according to Adedoyin (2003) and Torimiro (2008) are said to possess the following characteristics which includes greater physical strength, greater knowledge acquisition propensity, faster rate of learning, faster reaction time, innovative proneness, love for adventure and preference for boldness, minimal risk aversion, less fear of failure and less conversation. Youth status in society has been valued in various models. Checkoway and Gutierrez (2006) state that youth have been viewed as potential community assets for the last couple of decades, and are no longer viewed as a social problem. This is because young people are able to utilize their skills and make use of their rights to engage themselves in the development of their society (Checkoway, 2010; Head, 2011).

Furthermore, individual youth are able to create chances for personal development in terms of new skills and knowledge. The second is a communal benefit to society in an indirect way in which it is recognized as a social capital. This participation can contribute to and be reinforced by social development, organizational capacity, and positive changes in the community so that shared benefits can be dispersed to community members as a whole (Checkoway & Gutierrez, 2006). Therefore, the status of youth can be promoted through their social involvements. In the late 1990s the trade in major conventional weapons, though drastically reduced, still accounts for tens of billions of dollars annually. At the same time the proliferation of small arms and light weapons appears to have increased, as indicated below. This is taking place in an environment where even the loose discipline previously imposed by the US and Soviet Union on their allies and client States has largely disappeared. In today's world of internal conflicts and civil strife accountability is much more difficult to impose and is often non-existent. The availability of weapons is increasingly governed by the laws of supply and demand with little or no regard to the behaviour of recipients. In the current 'buyers' market' suppliers, whether States or companies, are notably reluctant to condition sales on the behaviour or purposes of belligerents.

For many years now, the global trade in major conventional weapons (such as tanks, fighter aircraft, naval ships and armored personnel carriers) has been documented by organizations such as the Stockholm International Peace Research Institute (SIPRI), the US Arms Control and Disarmament Agency, and more recently, the UN Register of Conventional Arms. The sale or transfer of these weapons in the 1970s and 1980s, both among NATO and Warsaw Pact members and from these alliances to developing countries, was relatively easy to track in terms of both trade flows and dollar amounts. Over time, the international community became increasingly concerned that the proliferation of major weapon systems was fueling regional arms races that could break out into open warfare (e.g., the Iran-Iraq war of the 1980s). The end of the Cold War was followed by a dramatic fall in global exports of major weapons systems, from a high of \$40.5 billion in 1984 to \$20 billion in 1994 (with a recent increase to \$25 billion in 1997). In the developing world, economic constraints and the loss of favourable terms of credit from the superpowers to finance arms sales have resulted in similar reductions in arms imports, from \$31 billion in 1987 to \$12 billion in 1994 (with an increase to \$18 billion in 1997). A significant development since the 1980s has been the emergence among developing countries of a number of new exporters of major weapons systems.

The proliferation of light weapons and illicit arms trafficking in Nigeria pose a major threat to peace, security and development in the continent. Although they do not in themselves cause the conflicts and criminal activities in which they are used, the wide availability, accumulation and illicit flows of such weapons tend to escalate conflicts; undermine peace agreements; intensify violence and impact on crime; impede economic and social development; and hinder the development of social stability, democracy and good governance. In the current world environment in which the realities of globalization are literally forcing the rapid break down of border lines, low-intensity conflicts in which small arms are critical, and widely used, are threatening the nonnegotiable core value (national security) of especially developing countries of Africa and indeed the countries of the West African sub-region including Nigeria.

The proliferation of small arms is thus a brisk business in the West African sub-region. It has become a serious matter of concern not just to all countries in the region but also to the international community. Dokunbo (2003) provides a graphic picture of the perturbing effects of small arms generally and in West Africa in particular: Of the 500,000 people killed every year across the world, an estimated 300,000 of them are as a result of small arms (Dokunbo, 2003). An estimated 50 percent of illicit weapons that proliferate in Africa are used in internal conflicts, armed robbery and drug trafficking. West Africa alone is reported to have an estimated eight million illicit weapons. Availability of small arms outside the formal security structures had contributed greatly in creating continuous cycle of violence and instability in which particularly women and children are brutalized. (Dokunbo, 2003). Experts have agreed that, "the proliferation of small arms and light weapons, rifles, handguns,

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machine guns grenades and bazookas - is just as harmful as the increasing number of so-called weapons of mass destruction. Of the 50 or so conflicts fought since the end of the Cold War, the vast majority of them have been fought predominantly with small arm". Although Nigeria has a manufacturing capacity for small arms through the Defence Industries Corporation of Nigeria (DICON), the emphasis in recent years has been on importing weapons rather than domestic manufacture. Such domestic manufacture has been for the Nigerian military and police (Adamu, 2012). The late military Head of State, General Sani Abacha spent US \$17 million on imported rifles despite DICON having large numbers on its inventory. Nigeria sought to revive talks with a South African arms company about a joint venture agreement. Many of the weapons illicitly in circulation in Nigeria have been imported.

At a United Nations Small Arms Conference in 2001, the Nigeria Minister of Defence confirmed that there were a million light weapons illicitly circulating in his country (Dokunbo, 2003). Light weapons are widely available in the delta. According to community leaders in this region, many villages have small annouries of AK-47s. As elsewhere in West Africa, the preference is for industrially manufactured weapons and the cost of procuring the e is high - an AK-47 with two magazines can sell for US\$1,700. In Warri, an oil-rich town in the delta, youths have openly hawked pistols and automatic rifles (referred to by local dealers as 'pure water') for between US\$200 and US\$400. Pistols can be much cheaper. The high cost of purchasing an AK -47 in the delta suggests that there is a scarcity value. Some informants suggested that prices fall during escalation of conflicts, but the volume of sales increases considerably (Akhoragbon, 2010). The same weapon is sold in Senegal or Cote d'Ivoire for US\$300 by traders from Liberia (Checkoway, 2006). Apart from the Niger Delta Volunteer Force, the other ethnic group that has acquired small arms and light weapons is the O'odua People's Congress (OPC). The widespread availability of light weapons in the Delta Region of Nigeria is a particular challenge. The criminalization and political economy of conflicts in the region are establishing a basis for escalated, protracted and entrenched violence. Factors that contribute to the destabilization of the region include illegal oil bunkering, ready availability of weapons, endemic corruption, high youth unemployment and social disintegration. Combined, they contribute the resources, weapons and foot soldiers for continued conflict (Chuma, 2011). Micro-level conflicts in the Niger Delta are part of a complex conflict system that is issue-based, ethnic and geographic in nature. Hundreds of criminal and politically motivated gangs have sprung up - many with eye-catching names such as Blood Suckers, Gentlemen's Club and the Royal House of Peace. Most of these are linked to well-known politicians.

The Niger Delta People's Volunteer Force and the Niger Delta Vigilante Group have attracted international attention because of their public profile in 2004 and threats to disrupt the oil industry - threats sufficient to have an impact on world oil prices for a short period (Dokubo, 2003). A key stimulant is illegal oil bunkering has grown significantly over the last few years. According to the federal government, some 300,000 barrel/day are illegally freighted out of the country, but some estimate the true cost lies between US\$1.5 billion and US\$4 billion. The figure can fluctuate greatly depending on political efforts to deal with the practice' Such illicit bunkering is fostered by the sense of poverty and inequality among youth in the delta: in a situation where many communities feel they do not legitimately benefit from the oil industry, it is easy for criminal groups to make illegal oil bunkering appeal (Head, 2011). The Delta provides these illicit networks with both a pool of unemployed youth and armed ethnic militias who know the terrain well. It is also characterized by a corrupt or ineffective law enforcement effort, coupled with a weak judicial process. The criminal networks also enjoy patronage from senior government officials and politicians, who use bunkering as a source of funds for political campaigning (Igidi, 2012). These local groups are also linked into international networks, both West Africa (from Sao Tome, Liberia, Senegal, Cote d'Ivoire and the Gambia) and International (involving Moroccans, Venezuelans, Lebanese and French). At a meeting on 1 October 2004 in Abuja with representatives of the federal government, the leaders of two of the main armed groups, the Niger Delta People's Volunteer Force under Alhaji Mujahid Abubakar Asari Dokubo and the Niger Delta Vigilante Group led by Ateke Tom, agreed to disband and disarm. There followed further meetings in late 2004, and a disarmament process under which 1,000 guns were handed over, the majority of them AK-47s or SA Vz 58s (Kawu, 2012). The condition of the weapons was poor, suggesting that the best weapons have been retained.

To enable communities to defend themselves against extremist groups, some States have armed militias or other non-state actors, whose weapons are even more likely to be diverted than those entrusted to official national security structures (Nte, 2011). For example, in Burkina Faso, the Government launched a programme in 2020 to arm citizens who joined the *Volontaires pour la defense de la patrie* (VDP), a national self-defence movement.³³ However, reportedly, VDP members are easy targets for extremists who target them both for their weapons and to deter any future collaboration with the State.³⁴ Meanwhile, in central Mali, self-defence militias such as *Dan Na Ambassagou*, are alleged to have received resources from sympathetic elements within the state security forces (Okafor, 2012). kunrotifa (2007) defined evaluation as the provision of

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information involving selection of criteria, collection of data and analysis for the sake of facilitating decision making. Therefore, this study evaluated sales of arms and ammunition among Nigerian youths in Riverine areas: a study of Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State. Youths are the major determiners of peace and stability of a nation. They are the foundation of a society. Their energies, inventiveness, character and orientation define the pace of development and security of a nation. Despite the important of youths in the society, it has been observed that proliferation of light weapons and illicit arms trafficking in Nigeria existed among them and this has posed a major threat to peace, security and development in the continent (Ola, 2011). Although they do not in themselves cause the conflicts and criminal activities in which they are used, the wide availability, accumulation and illicit flows of such weapons tend to escalate conflicts. As a way of addressing this problem, numerous studies have been carried on how to put an end to sales of arms and ammunition among Nigerian youths (Vines, 2005). All these studies came up with good contributions but with less research focus on evaluated sales of arms and ammunition among Nigerian youths in Riverine areas: a study of Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State. Therefore, this study evaluated evaluated sales of arms and ammunition among Nigerian youths in Riverine areas: a study of Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the attitude of youth to sales of arms and ammunition in riverine areas of Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State.

Research Question

What is the attitude of youth to sales of arms and ammunition in riverine areas of Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State?

Methodology

This study adopted the survey research design. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 150 youths in Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State. One instrument was used for data collection: Questionnaire on Sale of Arms and Ammunition Questionnaire ($r=0.78$). Data collected were analysed using percentage scores, mean and standard deviation.

Result

Research Question

What is the attitude of youth to sales of arms and ammunition in riverine areas of Eket Senatorial District, Akwa Ibom State?

Table 1: Attitude of Youth to Sales of Arms and Ammunition in Riverine Areas

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	St. D.
1	I like selling of arms and ammunition.	3.40	.820
2	I prefer selling of arms and ammunition to other business .	3.24	.791
3	I am favorable disclosed to selling of arms and ammunition.	3.35	.715
4	Selling of arms and ammunition does not require a lot of stress.	1.63	.689
5	Selling of arms and ammunition is profitable	3.29	.585
6	I discourage people from selling arms and ammunition	3.28	.735
7	If I have my way, I will not stop people from selling arms and ammunition	1.63	.679
8	Selling of arms and ammunition has connected me with many people	3.38	.729
9	Selling of arms and ammunition is burdensome.	1.63	.584
10	I am not comfortable with the selling of arms and ammunition	1.64	.532
11	I always enjoy selling of arms and ammunition.	3.48	.540
12	If I have my way, I wish selling of arms and ammunition is made legal.	3.43	.536
13	Selling of arms and ammunition increases my sources of income.	3.34	.577
14	Selling of arms and ammunition is not beneficial.	1.54	.597
15	Selling of arms and ammunition is a waste of time.	1.45	.550
16	Selling of arms and ammunition consumes more time than necessary.	1.58	.581
17	I am not encouraged to selling arms and ammunition	1.51	.564

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18	Selling of arms and ammunition is not convenient for me	3.34	.579
19	Selling of arms and ammunition does not guarantee good living.	3.41	.615
20	Selling of arms and ammunition does not promote peace.	1.78	.661

Weighted Mean = 2.56; Threshold = 2.50

Table 1 shows the attitude of youth to sales of arms and ammunition in riverine areas, Eket Senatorial District. The result indicates a weighted mean of 2.56 which is greater than the threshold set at 2.50. This result implies that majority of the selected youths had a positive attitude to sales of arms and ammunition.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 revealed that majority of the selected youths had a positive attitude to selling of arms and ammunition. This may be because the proliferation of light weapons and illicit arms trafficking in Nigeria pose a major threat to peace, security and development in the continent. This is similar to the study of Chuma (2011) who revealed that the availability of weapons is increasingly governed by the laws of supply and demand with little or no regard to the behaviour of recipients. This is contrary to the study of Dokunbo (2003) who reported that availability of small arms outside the formal security structures had contributed greatly in creating continuous cycle of violence and instability in which particularly women and children are brutalized.

Conclusion

The study has shown that majority of youths had a positive attitude to selling of arms and ammunition. This study has provided a better understanding of that majority of the selected youths had a positive attitude to selling of arms and ammunition riverine areas especially in Eket Senatorial district, Akwa Ibom State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that:

1. Government should provide job opportunities for the unemployed youths in the country.
2. Security personnel should be more proactive in maintaining peace in the country.
3. Youths should not be allowed to legalize the selling of arms and ammunition in the country. Anyone caught with unlawful possession of arms and ammunition should be arrested and charged to court.
4. Community leaders should work with government in maintaining peace and they should not condone criminals or criminal acts in their domain.

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